

ADVANTAGES OF DISTANCE EDUCATION IN LEARNING ENGLISH

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ELSEVIER

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Annotatsiya: Ingliz tilini masofadan o'rganish bepul - zamonaviy axborot texnologiyalaridan foydalanish imkoniga ega bo'lgan har bir kishi undan foydalanishi mumkin. Ushbu maqolada ingliz tilini masofaviy o'qitishning afzalliklari va ingliz tilini samarali o'qitishning bir qancha usullari, shuningdek, IT sohasidagi ba'zi ma'lumotlar va ingliz tilini o'rganishdagi zamonaviy ta'lim texnologiyalari maqolada yoritilgan

Keywords: Ingliz tili, masofaviy, axborot texnologiyalari, IT, kompyuter, innovatsiya, axborot-kommunikatsiya, ta'lim;

Abstract: Remote learning of the English language is free - anyone who has access to modern information technologies can use it. In this article, the advantages of distance learning English and several methods of effective English language teaching, as well as some information from the IT field and modern educational technologies in English language learning are highlighted in the article.

Keywords: English language, remote, information technology, IT, computer, innovative, information-communication, education;

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INTRODUCTION

After the independence of our country, the demand for learning foreign languages has increased sharply, our country is creating wide opportunities for language learning. Today, schools have modern computers, electronic resources, access to the Internet. The use of information technologies is possible not only at various stages of schoolchildren's training, but also in regular English lessons. The introduction of computer technologies in the scheme of the traditional lesson allows the teacher to work on the computer part of the educational process, the educational process is more interesting, colorful, intense. The computer cannot replace, but only complements teachers.

Computer involvement allows you to make any lesson attractive and truly modern. Completing any task, using the computer, using the lesson, creates an opportunity to increase the intensity of the lesson. Use of variable materials and operational plans help individualize learning. It can be used at all stages of

computer-based teaching: new materials, consolidation, repetition, knowledge management, and teaching of skills and abilities.

LITERATURE AND ANALYSIS METHODOLOGY

Today, we will discuss in detail about distance learning English, the features that make it different from regular classes, and how far IT is in distance learning English.

Speaking about the specific features, it is worth noting the advantages of distance education, which are available to all participants of the educational process (teacher and student): access to various sources of information; information of different volume and content the ability to receive; the ability to quickly communicate and transfer data of any size and type to any distance; the ability to study and complete assignments on an individual basis; the possibility of transitioning from oral teaching methods to methods of partial research, research and creative activity of students; the ability to significantly increase students' interest in learning English, which affects the memory, emotions, motivational sphere, the ability to learn computer skills.

The purpose of distance learning is not to teach ready-made facts and actions, but to teach the principles of orientation in the educational material, primarily with the help of sources. The ability to work with information arrays, find the necessary information, analyze it competently and use it for various purposes of knowledge - all this is becoming one of the main types of cognitive activity of students in modern and future schools.

The meaning of education is to create conditions for each student to learn, self-study, education, self-discipline, and development - creative self. -self development. Indispensable conditions for self-development are the development of independence and creativity, responsibility, initiative, and the style of personal educational activities. The student must evaluate the importance and difficulty of tasks, the time and effort spent, predict the possible consequences and results of his educational activities. In the process of distance education, the student himself becomes the creator of his education, he plans, organizes and analyzes his actions. All of this is in line with the main purpose of learning - teaching to learn.

RESULTS

Language is the main means of communication, without which it is difficult to imagine the existence and development of human society. Today, at a time when great changes are taking place in social relations in our world, communication media (information technologies) require the improvement of students' communicative skills. it is important that they exchange ideas in different situations during interaction with other participants of communication, and use language and speech norms correctly. In such conditions, the main purpose of a

foreign language is the formation of communicative skills, that is, it is required to carry out interpersonal and intercultural communication in a foreign language.

By the end of the 20th century, English had finally established itself as a world language. Its study became compulsory in most schools around the world and the teaching methodology began to develop by leaps and bounds.

DISCUSSION

Modernity puts higher demands on teaching practical knowledge of a foreign language in daily communication and professional field. Ways to increase the effectiveness of general education are being developed, and large amounts of money are being directed to the development and implementation of new information technologies. The use of information technology reveals the enormous potential of the computer as an educational tool. The IT field is especially important in the process of learning English. Also, computer-based learning programs have many advantages over traditional teaching methods.

They allow you to teach different types of speech activities and combine them in different combinations;

helping to understand linguistic phenomena, forming linguistic skills, creating communicative situations; automating language and speech movements; and providing the opportunity to take into account the leading representative system, implement an individual approach, and activate the student's independent work.

Teaching on a computer has a great motivational potential. Teachers try to use new modern technologies in their work. They use a variety of additional electronic manuals and programs, but this does not always correspond directly to the textbook. Therefore, at present, we are definitely obliged to develop didactic support for the lesson using multimedia technologies. A modern teacher should take into account that information and communication technologies (ICT) of education have become a part of life. The use of new information technologies expands the scope of the educational process, increases its practical orientation, increases students' enthusiasm for the educational process, develops intellectual and creative abilities of students, their independent acquisition of new knowledge and creative abilities. helps to form. conditions for successful self-realization in the future.

The computer in the educational process is not a mechanical teacher, a substitute or analogue of the teacher, but an active tool for the development of children, increasing and expanding the possibilities of their cognitive activity. The computer allows the teacher to allocate time for creative activities and create individual learning paths for students.

Teaching ICT in English classes is an effective pedagogical tool for learning foreign language culture and developing communication skills. ICT helps to speed up the learning process, increase students' interest in science, increases the quality of mastering the material, allows for individualization of the learning process, and prevents the subjectivity of evaluation. At the same time, modern educational materials in English are mainly didactic audio materials, so the resource capabilities of the Internet educational environment allow the use of new interactive materials and guides, as well as the ability of the teacher to independently develop slides. presentation with materials from sites. Foreign language teachers should thoroughly master the methodology of using ICT tools in organizing a student-oriented educational process.

In modern sources, information and communication technologies for the creation, transmission and distribution of information and the provision of services (computer hardware, software, telephone lines, cellular communication, e-mail, cellular and satellite technologies, wireless and cable) represents a wide range of digital technologies used. networks) communication, multimedia and Internet). The most commonly used ICT tools in the educational process include:

- electronic textbooks and training manuals displayed using a computer and a multimedia projector;
- electronic encyclopedias and references; simulators and test programs, educational resources on the Internet, DVDs and CDs with pictures and illustrations, video and audio equipment, research works and projects.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it should be said that modern language teaching is aimed at forming a more cultured person, who has the skills of self-analysis and systematization of new knowledge. Innovative methods are an integral part of the modernization of the entire system. This ensures that teachers can familiarize themselves with the most advanced approaches and then integrate them and use them in their work to achieve significant growth in the education system. Many organizations are moving to a new level by using multimedia capabilities to send and receive information. The use of computers and other devices determines the success of the entire educational process.

Sufficient attention should be paid to the formation of speech skills and the development of social flexibility in the training conducted during the educational process. In addition, the success of each lesson in education largely depends on the correct organization of the training.

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